

PredMicro: Fitting Predictive Microbial Models

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1 About PredMicro

Predictive Microbiology deals with the development of accurate and, at the same time, versatile mathematical models, able to describe the microbial evolution in food products as a function of environmental conditions, which are assumed to be measurable.

The **PredMicro** web application is a support tool for fitting the most widely used predictive microbiology primary growth models. These are models that describe microbial concentration as a function of time at constant environmental conditions.

Model **inputs** are:

- t : time, assuming time zero as the beginning of the experiment; and
- $Y_{(t)}$: the natural logarithm of the microbial concentration $X_{(t)}$ measured at time t .

Users should make sure that the microbial concentration input is entered in natural logarithm, $Y_{(t)} = \ln(X_{(t)})$.

The number of model **parameters** is dependent upon the completeness of the microbial growth curve. the following parameters can be estimated using this web application:

- Y_0 : the natural logarithm of the initial microbial concentration at $t = 0$;
- μ_{max} : maximum specific growth rate given in time $units^{-1}$;
- λ : duration of the lag phase in time units; and

- Y_{max} : the natural logarithm of the maximum concentration reached by the microorganism.

A **full model** should be adjusted to a complete microbial curve, where the lag phase, exponential phase and stationary phase can be identified. GrowthFit can also fit reduced models. A **no-stationary phase model** is to be adjusted to an experimental microbial curve that presents lag phase and exponential phase, whereas a **no-lag phase model** should be adjusted to an experimental curve composed of exponential phase and stationary phase. An experimental growth curve that presents only exponential phase cannot be analysed using the **PredMicro** web application.

2 Full growth models available in PredMicro

GrowthFit can adjust four nonlinear models to complete microbial growth curves: **Huang model**, **Rosso model**, **Baranyi & Roberts model** and the **reparameterised Gompertz model**.

2.1 Huang model

The Huang growth model was developed by Huang (2008).

$$Y_{(t)} = Y_0 + Y_{max} - \log(e^{Y_0} + (e^{Y_{max}} - e^{Y_0}) \times e^{-\mu_{max} \times B_{(t)}})$$

$$B_{(t)} = t + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times \log\left(\frac{1+e^{-\alpha \times (t-\lambda)}}{1+e^{-\alpha \times \lambda}}\right)$$

After evaluating multiple growth data sets, Huang (2013) recommended fixing the parameter α to 4.0. GrowthFit considers $\alpha = 4.0$.

2.2 Rosso model

The Rosso growth model is a simple two-phase model proposed by Rosso et al. (1996).

$$Y_{(t)} = \begin{cases} Y_0 & \text{if } t \leq \lambda \\ Y_{max} - \log\left[1 + \left(\frac{e^{Y_{max}}}{e^{Y_0}} - 1\right) e^{-\mu_{max}(t-\lambda)}\right] & \text{if } t > \lambda \end{cases}$$

2.3 Baranyi & Roberts model

The original Baranyi & Roberts model attributes the lag phase to the need to synthesise an unknown substrate q that is critical for growth, whose initial value q_0 is a measure of the initial physiological state of the microbial cells (Baranyi and Roberts (1994)).

PredMicro implements the Baranyi & Roberts model with basis on the transformation $h_0 = \mu_{max} \times \lambda$, in order to estimate λ . Thus, the model parameterisation used is:

$$Y_{(t)} = Y_0 + \mu_{max} \times A_{(t)} - \frac{1}{m} \times \log\left[1 + \frac{\exp(m \times \mu_{max} \times A_{(t)}) - 1}{\exp(m \times (\mu_{max} \times \lambda - Y_0))}\right]$$

$$A_{(t)} = t + \frac{\log[\exp(-\mu_{max} \times t) + \exp(-\mu_{max} \times \lambda) - \exp(-\mu_{max} \times t - \mu_{max} \times \lambda)]}{\mu_{max}}$$

Most of the times, the parameter m , which characterises the curvature before the stationary phase is assumed to be 1.0. GrowthFit simplifies this model by assuming $m = 1.0$.

2.4 Reparameterised Gompertz model

PredMicro adjusts the Gompertz model, as reparameterised by Zwietering et al. (1990) from the modified Gompertz model.

$$Y_{(t)} = Y_0 + (Y_{max} - Y_0) \times \exp \left[-\exp \left(\frac{\mu_{max} \times (\lambda - t)}{Y_{max} - Y_0} + 1 \right) \right]$$

3 No stationary phase growth models available in PredMicro

PredMicro can adjust three nonlinear models to microbial growth curves without stationary phase: reduced Huang model, reduced Baranyi & Roberts model and two-phase linear growth model

3.1 Huang model

This model is a special case of the complete Huang model, suitable for experimental growth curves that do not reach stationary phases.

$$Y_{(t)} = Y_0 + \mu_{max} \times \left[t + 0.25 \times \log \left(\frac{1 + e^{-4 \times (t - \lambda)}}{1 + e^{4 \times \lambda}} \right) \right]$$

3.2 Baranyi & Roberts model

This is a special case of the full Baranyi & Roberts model briefly presented above.

$$Y_{(t)} = Y_0 + \mu_{max} \times t + \log [\exp(-\mu_{max} \times t) + \exp(-\mu_{max} \times \lambda) - \exp(-\mu_{max} \times t - \mu_{max} \times \lambda)]$$

3.3 Two-phase linear model

This model is a reduced model of the three-phase linear growth model proposed by Buchanan et al. (1997).

$$Y_{(t)} = \begin{cases} Y_0, & \text{if } t \leq \lambda \\ Y_0 + \mu_{max} \times (t - \lambda), & \text{if } t > \lambda \end{cases}$$

4 No lag phase growth models available in PredMicro

PredMicro can adjust two nonlinear models to microbial growth curves that do not show lag phase: Richards model and Fang model.

4.1 Richards model

$$Y_{(t)} = Y_0 + \mu_{max} \times t - \frac{1}{m} \times \log \left(1 + \frac{\exp(m \times \mu_{max} \times t) - 1}{\exp(m \times (Y_{max} - Y_0))} \right)$$

4.2 Fang model

Fang et al. (2012) and Fang et al. (2013) integrated the logistic growth model, producing a continuous model that is particularly suitable for growth curves without lag phase.

$$Y_{(t)} = Y_0 + Y_{max} - \log [e^{Y_0} + (e^{Y_{max}} - e^{Y_0}) \times e^{-\mu_{max} \times t}]$$

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